

Experimental

Recrystallised *trans*-stilbene (0.2 g; m.p. 123°, lit.² 125°) in cyclohexane (10 ml) with iodine (1.3 mg) was taken in the first system. The second and third systems were similarly selected by passing O₂ and N₂ (for 10 min each), respectively, in stead of iodine. Each system was exposed to N₂-laser flashes for 1 h (applied voltage, 16 kV; P_{N₂} 40 torr; 65 ~ 70 flash per min).

The irradiated product was subjected to chromatography over neutral alumina (10 g) for the first and second systems. The eluants were separately collected and the residues obtained by evaporation were subsequently recrystallised from alcohol. The irradiated reaction mixture of the third system was partially evaporated and the supernatant liquid was carefully decanted in ice-cold condition. The residue was separated using an alumina column.

Results and Discussion

The products obtained from the first and second systems were identified as phenanthrene (m.p. 97°, lit.² 97°), and that of the third system was characterised as *cis*-stilbene by the usual chemical and spectral methods.

The sensitiser used in first and second systems favour in the formation of triplets during irradiation under N₂-laser and then to phenanthrene by the transfer of excited energy of the sensitiser to *trans*-stilbene. Thus, the *trans*-stilbene first isomerises to *cis*-stilbene (the intermediate) through singlet states and then cyclises to phenanthrene by triplets. The singlet¹ and triplet² mechanisms have been discussed by many workers.

In the third system the sensitiser does not help to produce triplet states, but rather singlet states are formed. Thus, it favours the formation of *cis*-stilbene.

The singlet excitation appears to be more feasible than the triplet state at room temperature. The singlet state gets populated with the sensitiser under the N₂-laser irradiation and forms *cis*-stilbene; thus, helping for the cyclisation with the consecutive *cis*-stilbene molecule to form phenanthrene. The successive abstraction of H atoms makes easy with the oxidants like iodine and oxygen. The higher phenanthrene yield in the oxygen used (i.e., second system) shows that oxygen is a stronger oxidant than the other oxidants used in the experiment. Thus the irradiation period is shorter under N₂-laser irradiation and gives higher yield than that irradiated under normal uv light.

Acknowledgement

The authors feel grateful to Dr. R. L. Gupta and Dr. H. Maurya for their discussion. Thanks are also due to the U.G.C., New Delhi, for the financial support.

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Studies on 2-Azetidinones. Part-I. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of *p,p'*-Bis(3-chloro-4-aryl-2-azetidinon-1-ylcarbamoylmethoxy)diphenylsulphones

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Manuscript received 13 June 1988, revised 27 September 1988, accepted 4 October 1988

A large number of antibiotics contain a β -lactam heterocyclic moiety¹. Also hydroxysulphones possess therapeutic properties². Keeping this in view, we have combined the two structures and synthesised some 2-azetidinone derivatives.

p,p'-Dihydroxydiphenylsulphone was condensed with ethyl chloroacetate to get the ester (1), which was then condensed with hydrazine hydrate to obtain *p,p'*-bis(hydrazinocarbonylmethoxy)diphenylsulphone (2). The latter was condensed with aromatic aldehydes to get the Schiff bases (3), which on treatment with chloroacetyl chloride in presence of triethylamine gave substituted 2-azetidinones (4). The structural assignments of the products were based on their elemental analysis, ir and pmr spectral data. The products were screened for their antimicrobial activity.

Antimicrobial activity: The antimicrobial screening of 2-azetidinone derivatives was carried out using cup-plate method³ at a concentration of 50 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ using gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus citreus*, gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Marcasane serrata* and fungi *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Aspergillus niger*.

The results showed that most of the compounds were moderately active against different strains of bacteria and fungi (10–20 mm, zone of inhibition). The maximum activity as observed in 2-azetidinone derivatives (4) when R=4-chlorophenyl, 3-methoxy-2-hydroxyphenyl and 4-hydroxyphenyl against *A. niger*, when R=2,6-dichlorophenyl and 3-methoxy-2-hydroxyphenyl against *M. serratia*, when R=2-nitrophenyl against *S. cerevisiae*.

Experimental

Melting points of the compounds were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The structures of the compounds were established on the basis of their elemental analysis and spectral data. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu DR-1, 435-IR spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a XL-100A, 100.1 MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal reference.

p,p'-Bis(hydrazinocarbonylmethoxy)diphenylsulphone (2): An aqueous solution of hydrazine hydrate (7 ml; 80%) was added to a suspension of *p,p'*-bis(carbomethoxymethoxy)diphenylsulphone (8.45 g, 0.02 mol) in ethanol (15 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 h and cooled to room temperature. The hydrazide thus separated on cooling was isolated and crystallised from DMF, (6.85 g, 87%), m.p. 228° (Found: C, 48.77; H, 4.57; N, 14.14. $C_{16}H_{18}O_6N_4S$ requires: C, 48.72; H, 4.60; N, 14.20%). ν_{max} (KBr) 3 300 (NH or NH_2 str.), 1 680 (C=O str.), 1 145, 1 290 (S=O str, asym. and sym. respectively) and 1 250 cm^{-1} (C–O–C str., asym.); δ (DMSO- d_6) 4.32 (4H, s, $2 \times NH_2$), 4.60 (4H, s, $2 \times H_2COAr$), 8.00–6.96 (8H, m, $2 \times ArH$) and 9.4 (2H, s, $2 \times CONH$).

p,p'-Bis(benzalhydrazinocarbonylmethoxy)diphenylsulphone (3): A mixture of benzaldehyde (2.02 ml, 0.02 mol) and *p,p'*-bis(hydrazinocarbonylmethoxy)diphenylsulphone (3.94 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol was

refluxed in presence of acetic acid (few drops) for 6 h. The reaction mixture was then poured over crushed ice and the product crystallised from ethanol, (3.88 g, 68%), m.p. 172° (Found: C, 63.12; H, 4.60; N, 6.84. $C_{30}H_{36}N_4O_6S$ requires: C, 63.14; H, 4.59; N, 9.82%). ν_{max} (KBr) 1 690 (C=O str., amide-I band), 1 650 (N=CH str.), 1 125, 1 300 (S=O str., asym. and sym. respectively) and 1 250 cm^{-1} (C–O–C str., asym.); δ (DMSO- d_6) 4.65 (2H, s, $2 \times RCH=N$), 5.13 (4H, s, $2 \times H_2COAr$), 8.17–6.75 (18H, m, $4 \times ArH$) and 11.36 (2H, s, $2 \times NHOC$), exchangeable with D_2O).

Similarly, other anils were prepared.

p,p'-Bis(3-chloro-4-aryl-2-azetidinon-1-ylcarbamoylmethoxy)diphenylsulphone (4): To *p,p'*-bis(benzalhydrazinocarbonylmethoxy)diphenylsulphone (2.85 g, 0.005 mol) in dry benzene (50 ml), chloroacetyl chloride (0.79 ml, 0.01 mol) was added slowly at room temperature with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was then stirred for 8 h after adding triethylamine (1.39 ml, 0.01 mol) and kept for 3 days. Excess of solvent was distilled off and the contents were poured into ice–water. The product was isolated and crystallised from dioxane–DMF (3:1), (2.32 g, 64%), m.p. 209° (Found: C, 56.40; H, 3.88; N, 7.76. $C_{24}H_{23}Cl_2N_4O_6S$ requires: C, 56.43; H, 3.90; N, 7.74%). ν_{max} (KBr) 1 715, 730 (C=O str., C–Cl str. respectively of β -lactam ring); 1 680 (C=O str., amide-I band), 1 140, 1 300 (S=O str., asym. and sym. respectively) and 1 250 cm^{-1} (C–O–C str., asym.); δ (DMSO- d_6) 3.59 (2H, s, $2 \times ArCH$), 4.74 (2H, s, $2 \times CHCl$), 5.24 (4H, s, $2 \times ArOCH_2$), 6.66–8.00 (18H, m, $4 \times ArH$), 8.20 (2H, s, $2 \times CONH$) and 11.34 (2H, d, $2 \times OH$ enolic).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF *p,p'*-BIS(3-CHLORO-4-ARYL-2-AZETIDINON-1-YLCARBAMOYL METHOXY)-DIPHENYLSULPHONES (4)*

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C
1.	Phenyl	209
2.	4-Tolyl	198
3.	2-Chlorophenyl	254
4.	4-Chlorophenyl	242
5.	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	266
6.	2,6-Dichlorophenyl	236
7.	2-Methoxyphenyl	263
8.	4-Methoxyphenyl	194
9.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	240
10.	3-Methoxy-2-hydroxyphenyl	165
11.	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl	232
12.	2-Nitrophenyl	206
13.	3-Nitrophenyl	248
14.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	246
15.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	148
16.	2-Hydroxy-3,5-dichlorophenyl	168
17.	4-Dimethylaminophenyl	228

*Yield: 50–74%, all compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. A. R. Parikh, Prof. and Head of the University Department of Chemistry,

Saurashtra University, Rajkot, for facilities. One of the authors (R.N.V.) thanks Gujarat State Government for awarding research scholarship and the other (K.P.R.) thanks U.G.C., New Delhi for awarding Junior Research Fellowship. Authors also thank to R.S.I.C., I.I.T., Bombay for the spectral analysis.

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Synthesis of 2,4-Disubstituted-1,5-quinoxalinodiazepines

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Manuscript received 18 May 1987, revised 26 September 1988, accepted 4 October 1988

DIAZEPINE derivatives possess wide therapeutic activity^{1,2}. With a view to get better therapeutic agents, we have prepared several new 2,4-disubstituted-1,5-quinoxalinodiazepines (3) by condensing 2,3-diaminoquinoxaline (1) and different 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds (2) in boiling ethanolic medium in presence of a little glacial acetic acid (Scheme 1). Compound 1 was prepared from oxamide and *o*-phenylenediamine. The structure of 3 was established on the basis of chemical analysis and ir spectral data.

Experimental

The required β -diketones (2) were prepared following the known procedure^{3,4}.

2,3-Diaminoquinoxaline (1): A mixture of the oxamide (12 g), *o*-phenylenediamine (14.8 g), dry dioxane (70 ml) and a few ml of dilute HCl was refluxed for 18 h. The solvent was then removed to get a solid which was dissolved in warm water (250 ml). The solution was cooled in an ice-bath to yield

Scheme 1

shiny yellow crystals (6 g) recrystallised from water, m.p. 331°d.

2,4-Disubstituted-1,5-quinoxalinodiazepines (3): Details of the typical experiment (where R=R'=phenyl) are as follows. A mixture of 2,3-diaminoquinoxaline (8 g), dibenzoylmethane (11.2 g), ethanol (75 ml) and glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and the precipitate formed was crystallised from ethanol, (56%), m.p. 125° (Found: C, 78.01; H, 4.30; N, 15.05. C₂₂H₁₆N₄ requires: C, 79.01; H, 4.50; N, 15.45%); its alcoholic solution gave a violet colouration with HCl indicating the diazepine structure; ν_{max} 1590 (C=N) and 1340 cm⁻¹ (C-N); δ 3.2 (2H, s, CH₂) and 6.9-8.32 (14H, m, ArH) (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3*

Compd. no.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅	M.p °C	Yield %
3a	H	H	H	H	H	125	56
3b	H	H	Cl	H	H	155	40
3c	H	H	Br	H	H	131	38
3d	H	H	OH ₂	H	H	98	39
3e	H	H	OOH ₂	H	H	149	39
3f	OH	H	H	H	H	138	40
3g	OH	Cl	H	H	H	220	45
3h	OH	H	H	Cl	H	221	45
3i	OH	OH ₂	H	H	H	150	48
3j	OH	OOH ₂	H	H	H	209	45
3k	OH	Cl	H	Cl	H	180	40
3l	OH	Br	H	H	H	141	48
3m	OH	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	185	40
3n	OH	H	H	H	H	238d	45
3o	OH	H	H	H	H	241d	40
3p	OH	H	Cl	H	H	248d	38
3q	OH	H	H	H	H	224d	38

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis. **Compounds a-m: R=phenyl; n: 2-pyridyl, o: 2-furyl, p: 2-furyl, q: 2-thienyl.